

Nigeria's Foreign Policy and Regional Leadership: Evaluating Its Impact on Security and Stability in West Africa

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Abstract

Background: Nigeria has consistently played a significant role in shaping the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and other regional organisations dedicated to promoting peace and security. As a key player in West Africa, Nigeria's foreign policy decisions greatly influence the region's security and stability. However, the long-term effects of these policies on regional stability remain inadequately explored, despite extensive research on Nigeria's foreign policy. Understanding how these actions impact regional security and stability is crucial for assessing the viability of Nigeria's foreign policy goals.

Objective: This study examined Nigeria's foreign policy actions and their impact on West Africa's security and stability.

Methodology: This study used a historical research approach. This approach is well-suited for analyzing complex issues in real-world contexts and offers valuable contextual insights.

Result: Although Nigeria's proactive approach strengthens regional security and reinforces its duty as a stabilizing force, the demands of these responsibilities often place pressure on domestic resources and create political instability. This finding shed insight into Nigeria's regional leadership ambitions and the difficulties it faces in balancing its domestic and international duties.

Conclusion: Nigeria faces challenges balancing its domestic needs with regional aspirations, as reflected in its foreign policy, specifically its leadership in ECOWAS. The country's global weaknesses, public dissent, security concerns, and socioeconomic burdens greatly hinder its capacity to fulfil regional obligations without jeopardising domestic interests.

Unique Contribution: The study provides theoretical evidence that Nigeria's leadership approach, characterised by its diplomatic efforts and economic strength, contributes to West Africa's security and stability.

Key Recommendation: The Nigerian government should leverage its leadership role in ECOWAS to foster discussions that address both domestic challenges and regional security threats. By organizing regional summits, it can promote cooperation and strengthen mutual understanding among member states.

Keywords: ECOWAS, security, stability, foreign policy, diplomatic initiatives

Introduction

Since its inception in 1975 under the name of ECOWAS, Nigeria has been using this platform to lobby for more economic cooperation and integration, influence the choice of the projects that might have significant impacts on the West African region, and discuss the issues of security in this area. Therefore, Nigeria enjoys a disproportionate decision-makers' role in respect of ECOWAS since the implementation of its policies and projects dictates the general fate of West Africa. This dual pattern of security and unity can be seen in Nigeria's diplomacy in the ECOWAS, especially an emphasis on the roles in security and development known as the Community's Security and Development Role (CSDR) (Ajakaiye, 2015).

With a defence pact, Nigeria has realised goals like trade liberalisation and the enforcement of ECOWAS conventions on the free movement, which has both unified and empowered the region. Nigeria consistently funds and implements these programmes, thus, vetting it as the leading security actor within the region. Ogunnubi & Amao (2016) opined that Nigeria, demonstrated by both quantitative and qualitative support through troops and resources, is geopolitically and tactically involved in the security of the West African region, though with hegemonic impossibility.

Nigeria's proactive approach has positioned it as the largest security provider within ECOWAS, setting the framework for addressing regional security threats. The country's leadership and membership in ECOWAS are firmly grounded in its foreign policy. As one of the most economically influential nations in West Africa, Nigeria prioritises regional unity and security in its foreign policy. ECOWAS leadership has positively impacted a more stabilised and more formidable region, which is in line with the Nigerian approach towards solving security issues (Bach, 2007). Nigeria has also led in the region's Dispute resolution, justice, and peace.

Objectives of the Study

This study examined Nigeria's foreign policy and its contribution to security and stability in West Africa. It also analysed the effectiveness of Nigeria's regional leadership in conflict resolution and economic integration across the region.

Literature Review

That part of politics that defines the relationships of Nigeria with other countries is referred to as Nigeria's foreign policy. Nigeria is seen as the regional power in West Africa, as captured by the ability to initiate, but also actively engage in the resolution of regional crises and ensure sustainable stability. These elements underscore Nigeria's significant influence not only in determining its own future but also in shaping the broader future of the continent (Ruto, 2015). While stability pertains to the economic, political, and social structures within West Africa, security involves the measures taken to protect people and states from various risks. Ensuring security is thus supported

by stability, which allows for effective management of potential contingencies through standardised security measures.

Advancing peace and development in the subregion relies on these dynamics, particularly given the strengths and challenges within the West African Monetary Zone (WAMZ), which is notable for its economic and demographic significance and Nigeria's strategic objectives. Nigeria's commitment to maintaining peace in West Africa reflects an ideological stance on African renaissance and the goal of reducing dependency on foreign resources. This, in turn, serves as a security measure against conflicts that could potentially spill over Nigeria's borders (Olaniyan, 2013).

Nigeria's involvement is especially prominent in the creation and support of regional security frameworks. For example, the 1981 Mutual Assistance in Defence Pact laid the groundwork for subsequent peacekeeping operations, collective security, and cooperation within ECOWAS. Nigeria was instrumental in both formulating and implementing this protocol, aligning several of its foreign policy goals with the security structure of ECOWAS. A notable milestone in Nigeria's role in regional peacekeeping was the establishment of the ECOWAS Monitoring Group (ECOMOG) in 1990, composed of Nigerian troops. ECOMOG's interventions in Liberia and Sierra Leone showcased ECOWAS's ability to respond regionally to domestic crises (Adejumobi and Ake, 2009). As such, Nigeria continues to support reforms that would enhance ECOWAS's capacity to address security challenges as its security architecture evolves. Militarily, Nigeria holds an important role in the political and economic aspects of ECOWAS, working to prevent war and support post-war reconstruction (Ogunnubi & Amao, 2016). Thus, Nigeria makes sure that its foreign policy goals support the goals and objectives of ECOWAS resulting to a stronger, safer and more stable region: *Civilizational Perspective in the Analysis of Nigeria's Foreign Policy Decisions in ECOWAS* Earlier it was mentioned that the official position of Nigeria is to become the dominant power in West Africa, which sets country's foreign policy priorities in the framework of activity within ECOWAS.

Given its significant economic and demographic influence in the region, Nigeria's political leadership is driven by the desire to implement policies that will yield favourable outcomes domestically. Nigeria seeks to lead in promoting stability in West Africa by utilising its influence within ECOWAS to drive the organisation's agenda, with a focus on peace and security. This drive for regional dominance is further propelled by Nigeria's attempts to keep other potential regional contenders to the throne, like Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire/Bach (Ruto, 2015). Ogunnubi and Amao (2016) posit that through membership in ECOWAS, Nigeria is privileged to keep hegemonic control over the West African sub-region that could, otherwise, pose a threat. The other reason for Nigeria's foreign policy in ECOWAS is security because Nigeria aims at maintaining the stability of neighbouring countries in order to avoid being affected by the disturbances in such countries. West Africa has been plagued with different forms of insecurity, for example civil conflicts, rebellions and transnational crimes. Their practical interest has been evident in Nigeria's consistent support for peace keeping operations; in Liberia, Sierra Leone and Mali in their capacities as members of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). Nigeria's mission in Liberia can be seen as both humanitarian: helping Liberia and as selfish, since Nigeria wanted to keep the civil war in Liberia from spilling over into Nigeria. Also, in recent times,

Fundamentalism, which began with Boko Haram, has stressed the need for regional security for countries in the Sahel region, for instance. With regard to security cooperation, intelligence sharing and coordination, Nigeria engages in and hosts some of these activities through ECOWAS in order to protect its borders from insecurity threats. Nigeria's security-oriented policies within ECOWAS align with its regional and national security interests (Orhero & Okolie, 2023). Nigeria's foreign policy within ECOWAS is significantly influenced by self-interest, particularly regarding its strategic economic priorities. The country seeks to enhance regional trade, streamline tariffs, and ease border crossings, all of which contribute to its economic growth (Ikejiaku, 2009). Nigeria's engagement with ECOWAS also includes supporting infrastructure development to enhance regional connectivity and commerce. According to Ogunnubi and Amao (2016), Nigeria views ECOWAS as an opportunity to strengthen its economic leverage in the region, with initiatives like capital, goods, and services exports. The improved ECOWAS, through the support of regional integration, decreases the extent to which the region depends on other markets, which is essential for Nigeria's future economic objectives. Also, Nigeria's foreign policy within the context of ECOWAS is also anchored on Pan-Africanism doctrine as well as the principles of reciprocity within the African continent. Being a significant supporter of the African unity and peace, Nigeria senses that it is responsible for the West Africa region's steadiness and integration since joining the ECOWAS (Okeke & Aniche, 2019). Adebajo highlights that Nigeria supports ECOWAS because of its belief in collective security and the principle that Africa must manage its own affairs.

Nigeria's Foreign Policy and Its Leadership in the Economic Community of West African States

According to Adebajo (2002), Nigerian policy has been both idea and security based. This has placed Nigeria in a strategic position to have an active voice in the formulation and execution of the policies of the ECOWAS, especially in economic cooperation, integration and defence (Okeke & Aniche, 2019). Nigeria envisioned a united and secure West Africa, where economic integration would foster peace and stability, influencing the establishment of ECOWAS in 1975. Since then, Nigeria has sought and achieved a leading role in ECOWAS, consistently taking the initiative to address regional security challenges (Adejumobi & Ake, 2009). In their views, regarding assertiveness of Nigeria's foreign policy postures, Ogunnubi and Amao (2016) opine that Nigerian hegemonic stability theory dominates decision-making in ECOWAS. Nigeria has shown this leadership by participating in peace-making missions in Liberia, Sierra Leone and recently in Côte d'Ivoire by dispatching Nigerian troops under ECOMOG. These humanitarians and the strategically intended interventions were central in preserving order in West Africa and averting conflict. In this respect, via ECOMOG, Nigeria has solidified its role as a security opportunist in the region and has shaped the way ECOWAS will respond to future security threats. Nigeria's dominance in peacekeeping has been central to the region's stability and its approach to conflict prevention and crisis management (Ogunnubi & Amao, 2016). Under Nigeria's leadership, ECOWAS has made institutional advances, including an improved framework for addressing security challenges. Nigeria's significant contributions to the ECOWAS budget have supported regional projects, including infrastructure development and poverty reduction, helping to maintain stability by addressing economic instability.

Despite challenges such as domestic political issues, limited funding, or internal struggles, Nigeria's continued commitment to ECOWAS, especially in the area of security, it underscores its

commitment to maintaining regional stability (Okeke & Aniche, 2019). Nigeria has a significant level of control over policies governing infrastructural development, trade liberalisation, and poverty reduction as part of governance stability within the West African region's largest economy (Orhero & Okolie, 2023). Also, the Nigerian foreign policy goals in relation to democracy and good governance are paramount to ECOWAS politics, which Nigeria supports and encourages for a stabilised polity. According to Adebajo (2002), Nigeria has been at the forefront in the formulation and development of ECOWAS policies on what he termed unconstitutional changes of government, hence checking political vigilantism, which ordinarily breeds political instability experienced in the form of coups in the region.

The Effect of Nigeria's Leadership on Regional Stability

The Sahel region has in the recent past become a nucleus of insurgent and terrorist groups, including Boko Haram and ISWAP, which have been posing a challenge to the authority of the government and indeed threatening regional security in West Africa. Kidnapping has also become a common problem facing Nigeria (Ameh, 2025). This article basically discusses Nigeria's robust involvement in the security formation of ECOWAS, especially against terrorism and insurgency in the Sahel region. In view of the fact that Nigeria is on the receiving end of Boko Haram's operations, particularly in the northeastern regions, counterterrorism is both a national imperative and a regional response. Bachmann and Schenoni (2018) highlight that Nigeria has effectively mobilized resources for initiatives such as the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF), which involves Nigeria, Niger, Chad, and Cameroon, demonstrating Nigeria's military strength and political influence within ECOWAS. Nigeria shows its dedication to regional peace by working with neighbouring nations to fight Boko Haram and ISWAP through the MNJTF. In addition, Nigeria has been involved in the formulation of the ECOWAS policies on intelligence, borders and security, which are crucial in the fight against other cross-boundary security issues. According to Sanda and Garuba (2020), Nigeria's leadership has enhanced the regional security frameworks, helped to promote parity in sharing the burdens within ECOWAS, and realised regional stabilisation of Sahelian security risks.

The Gulf of Guinea (GoG), another conflict-prone area, faces significant challenges such as organised crime, piracy, and illegal fishing, which disrupt both regional and international trade. As the biggest economy in the West African region, Nigeria prioritises stability in the GoG, especially since its own economy relies heavily on maritime trade. As for these challenges, Nigeria has been in the vanguard of leadership in both the ECOWAS and the Gulf of Guinea Commission and has, in fact, fought piracy both professionally and physically. For instance, Nigeria has lately especially focused on the development of naval forces, the programmes like the "Deep Blue Project" initiated in 2019, aiming at the enhancement of the security system in the area. This has involved the use of patrol vessels, reconnaissance aircraft, and advanced communication systems, and has helped boost maritime security and check on piracy (Okeke & Aniche, 2019). According to Osinowo (2015), Nigeria's leadership has signed the 2013 Yaoundé Code of Conduct to boost cooperation on security, particularly maritime, in the Gulf of Guinea and will place Nigeria more firmly on regional security. For lasting peace in the Sahel and Gulf of Guinea, ECOWAS must continue addressing these crises, and Nigeria's leadership has played a key role in strengthening the organisation's capacity. As a leading member of ECOWAS, Nigeria has been deeply involved in decision-making processes related to political, military, and economic aspects of peacekeeping

and stability. Adebajo (2002) emphasised Nigeria's initial participation in peacekeeping missions in Liberia and Sierra Leone, establishing a precedent for rapid military action before implementing diplomatic solutions. According to Oluwaseun and Isike (2018), Nigeria's ongoing support has made ECOWAS more effective in crisis response, positioning the organisation to better tackle security threats in both the Sahel and the Gulf of Guinea. Beyond military efforts, Nigeria actively tackles root causes like poverty and unemployment, which fuel insecurity, by backing development initiatives within ECOWAS. Nigeria's economic support to ECOWAS has centred on development, trade, and infrastructure projects, promoting deeper regional integration and stability (Ogunnubi & Amao, 2016).

Nigeria's Challenges in Balancing Domestic Needs with Regional Responsibilities

Nigeria faces numerous challenges in managing its domestic and regional responsibilities effectively. These include:

Domestic Political Turbulence: Internal political instability has hindered Nigeria's leadership role within ECOWAS. Military regimes, electoral violence, and domestic conflicts have often redirected resources and attention away from advancing regional integration efforts.

Economic Constraints: Despite being an economic powerhouse, Nigeria grapples with significant economic difficulties. Volatile global oil prices, poor economic governance, and pervasive corruption have weakened its ability to consistently provide financial support to ECOWAS initiatives.

Regional Rivalries: Nigeria's dominant position within ECOWAS has sometimes caused friction with other member states. Leadership competition and rivalries have occasionally disrupted collective decision-making and hampered effective cooperation within the organisation.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on the Hegemonic Stability Theory (HST), which was postulated by political scientist Charles P. Kindleberger in the 1970s. Kindleberger claimed that management of the saver currency provides four public focal points for sustaining global economic stability. This work was expanded by Kindleberger (1970), who postulated that the international economic order is best managed when a single power, or hegemon, leads and provides public goods to a system. He insisted that a condition of no hegemon, as was evidenced in the period between the two great wars, breeds disorder and cycles of depression. Raymond Aron (1966), Robert Gilpin (1981) and David P. Rapkin (1990) have later developed this theory into a framework for analysing the relations between states and their power in the global system. According to HST, the presence of a hegemon that controls and supplies essential public goods, such as security and economic stability, increases the likelihood of international systems remaining stable. The hegemon's ability and willingness to maintain order and stability can significantly influence the behavior of other states within the system. As Nigeria is the most populous and also the most economically influential country in West Africa, the country plays an unofficial role as a leader in the area provided by ECOWAS. For interpreting Nigeria's prominent position in regional politics, it is essential to take into account the country's economic potential, most notably its oil resources. In line with HST, the continuous formation and sustenance of regional hegemony is firmly associated with economic power. This aspect of the theory makes a lot of sense to Nigeria's capability of providing options in terms of trade, investment, and possible economic assistance to other

countries in the West African region (Ogunnubi & Amao, 2016). A central tenet of HST is that the hegemon provides security. Nigeria's engagement in regional conflicts, such as those in Liberia and Sierra Leone, underscores its role in preserving stability through both military and diplomatic interventions. By participating in peacekeeping missions and conflict resolution, Nigeria fulfils the duties of a regional leader in ensuring security and promoting regional governance (Adebajo, 2002). This influence enables Nigeria to demand for policies that will foster region stability and national interest at the same time. It is regrettable that, facing these challenges, Nigeria appears as a regional leader with difficulty, internal security problems, economic limitations, and opposition to foreign policy decisions.

HST is evident in Nigeria's leadership within ECOWAS, where it plays a key role in shaping the organisation's policies and strategic direction. The hegemon often has a disproportionate influence on the decisions and actions of regional institutions, leading to more effective group efforts in addressing security challenges (Adebajo, 2002). Hegemonic Stability Theory acknowledges that internal weaknesses can threaten the stability of a hegemon, potentially leading to regional instability (Krastev, 2019). While recognising the internal and external challenges Nigeria faces, HST highlights the country's critical role in regional stability. This theoretical framework helps deepen the understanding of Nigeria's foreign policy and its impact on the security and stability of the West African region.

Conclusion

These strategic, financial, security, political and cultural factors all form the context within which the foreign policy of Nigeria within ECOWAS is made. Its leadership role in ECOWAS is based on ambitions for regional supremacy, regional security, economic cooperation, Pan-African goals, and international recognition. Nigeria sees the ECOWAS as an appendage through which it can wield influence and politically engender stability in the region across West African states. In the light of demonstrated commitment to crisis intervention and peacekeeping as well as asserting its leadership in regional security, Nigeria has deployed its foreign policy interests into the ECOWAS composite. Its significance in the organisation has been the enhancement of the organisation's ability to promote stability in West Africa. It was influential in the protection of national interest and boosted the security of the sub-region. It means that Nigeria consolidates the leading position in the region of ECOWAS and strengthens its hegemony by building the security and stability of West Africa. In regions facing persistent security challenges, such as the Sahel and the Gulf of Guinea, Nigeria's leadership within ECOWAS has been crucial in addressing threats like organised crime, terrorism, and piracy. These issues require a unified regional approach for effective resolution. As the largest country in terms of population and the most developed economy in West Africa, Nigeria takes the leading role in creating a collective force aimed at maintaining or restoring stability in the region through the use of security measures. Through peace missions, Nigerian economic investments, and regional integration, Nigeria serves its own interests as well as those of the entire West African region. This active diplomacy strengthens Nigeria's position and its leading role in the provision of regional security and cooperation in the framework of the Goals of ECOWAS's Foreign Policy and those of this country.

Therefore, Nigeria's internal conditions will also have to be effectively managed if the country is to sustain its leadership in the region and the twin goals of stability and development for the benefit of its people. To strengthen Nigeria's leadership within ECOWAS while meeting internal needs, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The Nigerian government should use its leadership position to encourage debate within ECOWAS that can deal with internal issues as well as regional insecurity. Several summits could help to bring together member states with humanitarian, economic and security themes in order to improve their relationships.
- ii. The government should 'popularize' participation in the ECOWAS programmes so that the regional objectives are people oriented. Engagement of Nigerian local communities would therefore encourage them to support the country's foreign policy as well as counteract any resistance to regional initiatives in Nigeria.
- iii. To decisively confront domestic insurgencies and general insecurity in Nigeria, the welfare of the military and intelligence personnel needs to be improved. This could involve enhancing the knowledge base of security staff, raising the defense budget, and enhancing cooperation in sharing intelligence with surrounding countries.
- iv. To address the concern of answering the ECOWAS commitments in Nigeria, Nigerian policymakers need to develop synergy with private organisations to jointly finance and implement most of the regional activities. The realisation of PPPS may imply the generation of funds for regional and domestic endeavours and the general provision for appropriate resource allocation.

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